

A new bibenzyl compound from *Dendrobium gratosissimum*

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Abstract : A new bibenzyls compound, Isomoniliformine A, 1-{(7-hydroxy-5-methoxy-6-(18-(hydroxylmethyl)oxiranyl)-16,18-dimethoxyphenoxy)-phenyl}-2-(11-methoxyphenyl)ethane, was isolated from stems of *Dendrobium gratosissimum* Rchb. f. The structure of this unusual bibenzyl compound was determined by chemical and spectroscopic methods, particularly one- and two-dimensional ^1H and ^{13}C NMR.

Keywords : *Dendrobium gratosissimum*, Orchidaceae, bibenzyl derivative, isomoniliformine.

Shi-hu (Herba Dendrobii) is a commonly used Chinese herbal drug for nourishing "Yin" and clearing heat. A survey of the resource revealed that over 39 species (Orchidaceae) are used as a Yin tonic to nourish the stomach, promote the production of body fluid and reduce fever¹. It is the fresh or dried stem of *Dendrobium fimbriatum*, *D. candidum* and *D. nobile* Lindl. and its similitude species from the same genus (Orchidaceae) according to the Chinese Pharmacopoeia (2005). Previous phytochemical investigations on herbal Dendrobii have shown the presence of bibenzyls, phenanthrene, sesquiterpenes, alkaloids and so on². To our knowledge, no phytochemical work on *D. gratosissimum* Rchb. f. has been reported. In the course of our studies concerning the bioactive principles of herbal Dendrobii, a series of chemical components from *D. gratosissimum* Rchb. f. have been observed³. The present communication describes the isolation and characterization of a new bibenzyl derivative called hereafter Isomoniliformine from the EtOAc extract of stems.

Experimental

IR spectra were obtained using Perkin-Elmer model 1600 series FTIR. MS measures on JMSD-300 and HP5989A spectrometer. UV spectra were obtained Shimadzu UV-2200 UV/VIS spectrometers. NMR spectra were run on a ACF-500 Bruker spectrometer with TMS as internal standard. Column chromatographic separations were carried out using silica gel H-60 (Qingdao Haiyang Chemical Group Corporation, Qingdao, People's Republic of China), Sephadex LH-20 (Pharmacia Biotech AB, Uppsala, Sweden), as packing materials, and a Lichroprep

RP-18 (40–63 μm), GF₂₅₄ silica gel TLC plates (Qingdao Haiyang Chemical Group Corporation, Qingdao, People's Republic of China) were used for analytical TLC.

Stems of *D. gratosissimum* Rchb. f. were collected in ShiMao YYunNan province (China) and identified and authenticated by Xu Luoshan (Department of Pharmacognosy, China Pharmaceutical University, Nanjing, China). A voucher specimen was deposited in the Department of Pharmacognosy, Nanjing (number BQ-2004-05).

Dried powdered stems (5.0 kg) of *D. gratosissimum* Rchb. f. were extracted with hot EtOH (95%) for three times, followed by solvent evaporation under reduced pressure to yield the crude extract (500 g). Ethyl acetate extract gives EtOAc (260 g). The EtOAc extract (250 g) was subjected to silica gel column eluted with petroleum ether-ethyl acetate stepwisely (98 : 2 \rightarrow 60 : 40) and afforded four fraction [A (1.1 g), B (0.5 g), C (5.6 g), D (12.7 g)]. Fraction D was further purified by silica gel CC eluted with petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (5 : 1) and purified on Sephadex LH-20 CC eluted with CHCl_3 -MeOH (1 : 1) to yield compound **1** (200 mg).

Isomoniliformine A (**1**) :

Colorless solid crystal (MeOH); m.p. 163–164 °C; ν_{max} (MeOH) : 278.4, 257.8, 212.4 nm; IR bands (KBr, solvent, nujol) : 3440, 1592, 1500, 1480, 1411 cm^{-1} ; ESI-MS m/z : 482.1 (95.3), 210.1 (100), 182.4 (18.8), 153.1 (35.9); ^1H , ^{13}C NMR spectral data were showed in Table 1.

Results and discussion

Compound **1** was obtained as a colorless crystal with

Note

Table 1. ^1H , ^{13}C NMR spectra data for **1** (CDCl_3 , in 500 MHz, J in Hz and δ in ppm)

C	δ_{H}	δ_{C}	C	δ_{H}	δ_{C}
1	2.88 (m)	37.9	16		147.3
2	2.83 (m)	37.5	17	6.67 (s)	104.2
3		134.4	18		127.3
4	6.33 (d, J 1.5 Hz)	104.9	19	6.67 (s)	104.2
5		148.5	20		147.3
6		131.1	21	4.95 (d, J 8.2 Hz)	76.5
7		144.2	22		78.3
8	6.52 (d, J 1.5 Hz)	109.5	23	3.56 (dd, J 3.6, 12.6 Hz) 3.91 (dd, J 2.7, 12.6 Hz)	61.6
9		143.2	5-OMe	3.86 (s)	56.1
10	6.74 (d, J 1.0 Hz)	114.3	9-OMe	3.79 (s)	55.1
11		159.2	16,20-OMe	3.93 (s)	56.4
12	6.75 (dd, J 1.0, 5.2 Hz)	111.2			
13	7.20 (ddd, J 2.1, 6.5, 5.5 Hz)	129.3			
14	6.79 (dd, J 1.0, 7.7 Hz)	120.9			
15		135.3			

a quasi-molecular ion peak $[\text{M}+1]^+$ at m/z 483.15 in the ESI-MS (HRESIMS : 482.16, calcd. 482.85, positive mode) suggesting a molecular formula $\text{C}_{27}\text{H}_{30}\text{O}_8$. Strong absorptions bands at 1618, 1592, 1567, 1525, 1493 and 1432 cm^{-1} in the IR (KBr) spectrum exhibited the presence of benzene groups, which was confirmed by the carbon signals in the ^{13}C NMR spectrum.

In ^1H NMR spectrum of **1**, characteristic signals of bibenzyls at δ 2.83 (2H, m) and 2.88 (2H, m) were assigned to the two methylene groups, so a bibenzyl skeleton was proposed to the structure of compound **1**. The ^1H NMR spectrum also showed the signals for one phenolic hydroxyl proton (δ 5.60 ppm, 5-OH), four methoxyl groups [δ 3.86 (C₃-OMe), 3.79 (C₉-OMe), 3.93 (C_{16,20}-OMe)], eight aromatic proton and four aliphatic protons. Among the eight aromatic protons, the two protons at δ

6.33 (1H, d, J 1.5, H-2) and 6.52 (1H, d, J 1.5, H-2) exhibit a typical AB splitting pattern of meta-related doublet of A ring, two protons at δ 6.77 (2H, s, H-17,19) correspond to two symmetrical signals of C ring, four protons at δ 7.20 (1H, ddd, J 2.1, 6.5, 7.7 Hz, H-12), 6.79 (1H, ddd, J 7.7, 6.5 Hz, H-11), 6.75 (1H, dd, J 2.1, 6.5 Hz, H-10) and 6.74 (1H, d, J 1.0 Hz, H-8) were assigned to signals of B ring, which is similarly with signals of A ring from compound batatasin-III^A. Four proton signals at δ 3.5~5.0 showed the shape of glycerol [δ 4.95 (1H, d, J 8.2 Hz, H-21), 3.99 (1H, ddd, J 8.2, 3.6, 2.7 Hz, H-22) and 3.56 (2H, dd, J 3.6, 12.7 Hz, H-23a) and 3.91 (2H, dd, J 2.7, 12.7 Hz, H-23b)]. The ^1H - ^1H COSY spectrum showed the connectives of C-11 and C-12, C-2 and C-6, C- α and C- β (Fig. 1). The complete assignment of proton and carbon signals were

Fig. 1. Selected HMBC correlations (H→C) for isomoniliformine A (**1**).

determined by an HMBC experiment which showed long-range correlations between 17-OCH₃ with C-17; 3-OCH₃ with C-3; H-14 with C-1,2,6; H-13 with C-1,7,12; the combination of C-18 and C-21 can be proved by the correlations between H-21 and C-17,19 (Fig. 1).

Compound **1a** was obtained by all acetyl reaction of compound **1** (paratoluene sulfonic acid, sodium salt, room temperature). The chemical shifts of H-23 [δ 4.01 (dd, *J* 4.3, 12.3 Hz), 4.38 (dd, *J* 4.3, 12.3 Hz)] and H-22 [δ 4.24 (dt, *J* 7.5, 4.2 Hz)] are changed about +0.5 ppm and +0.3 ppm, respectively, by comparing with which of compound **1**, but the chemical shifts of H-21 is not changed almost through this reaction. So, the oxiranyl ring was confirmed between C-21 and C-22. As the result of above analysis, the structure of **1** was determined as 1-[(7-hydroxyl-5-methoxy-6-(18-(hydroxymethyl)

oxiranyl)-16,18-dimethoxyphenoxy)-phenyl]-2-(11-methoxyphenyl)ethane, has been named isomoniliformine A shown in Fig. 1. In the same time, we also found this compound in the stems of *D. nobile* Lindl.

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